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Analysis of Recommendation System Models

MASTER'S THESIS

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1 Introduction

1.1 Description of the topic

In my thesis, I study recommendation system models. Recommendation systems are software systems that aim to recommend certain items to users, based on their previous likes, dislikes, interactions, textual or numerical ratings, etc. Nowadays it is very important for online media and commercial sites to retain their customers, and they can easily do this by offering them more and more personalized interesting content. Recommendation systems provide a personalized user experience, by helping every single consumer identify and discover their favorite movies, TV shows, digital products, books, articles, services, and more. These systems help businesses increase sales and benefit consumers.

The concept behind recommendation algorithms is finding patterns in similar consumer behavior towards a service or product. At the core, a recommendation system employs a machine learning algorithm whose job is to predict the users' preferences, e.g. ratings, for a particular entity.

We can recommend products to users in different ways. The first and maybe the easiest way is to recommend the items to a user that are the most popular among all the users. This method is referenced as TopPopular in my thesis. Another way is to use some kind of predefined similarity function for the recommendations. These methods are explained in Section 1.3. Yet another one of the most used methods for recommendation is matrix factorization (Section 1.4).

For building a recommendation system, we need data in order to train the models. Regarding the data one can use for a recommendation system, there are two main types, implicit and explicit data. Explicit data is information that is provided intentionally, i.e., input from the users such as movie ratings. Implicit data is information that is not provided intentionally but gathered from passively available data streams, for example search history, clicks, order

history, etc. In this thesis I only consider models and algorithms using explicit data.

The recommendation itself can also be of several different types. It is possible to recommend a list of items for a user. A good illustration could be the following: given a user of a movie streaming service, we would like to name 5 movies that they will most probably like. The length of the list can be arbitrary of course.

It is also possible to predict a binary value, whether the user is going to like an item or not. An even more granular way is predicting a rating for an item on a specific scale (for example on the scale of 1-5).

1.2 Related research

Various approaches have been explored to enhance the user experience by providing personalized recommendations. These approaches range from traditional methods such as user or item similarity and content-based recommendation to more advanced techniques like matrix factorization and neural network models.

Collaborative filtering [1], [2] is a popular recommendation technique that relies on user-item interactions. This method is known for its simplicity and effectiveness. On the other hand, content-based recommendation [3] focuses on the attributes and features of the items.

Matrix factorization [4], [5] is a special collaborative filtering technique used to represent the user-item interaction matrix as the product of two lower-dimensional matrices, one representing users and the other representing items. This approach allows the model to capture latent factors representing user preferences and item characteristics, resulting in more accurate recommendations.

With the advent of deep learning, neural network models have become increasingly popular for recommendation tasks. These models can capture complex patterns and relationships in the data that traditional methods may

miss. Neural networks can learn even non-linear functions, whereas the matrix factorization model is only able to learn linear functions. Some notable neural network approaches include autoencoders [6], recurrent neural networks [7] or graph neural networks [8].

1.3 Methods based on similarity

It seems natural to consider either the similarity of users or the similarity of items when making recommendations. These play a fundamental role in providing personalized suggestions to users. In this section, we will explore two prominent techniques within this framework: collaborative filtering and content-based recommendation. Collaborative filtering relies on the collective preferences of users in the form of past interactions to make recommendations, while content-based recommendation focuses on factual information such as characteristics of items to generate personalized suggestions. It is important to mention that while past interactions are mostly abundantly available, factual data is a rather limited source of information. Let us get to know each method to understand their principles and applications in recommendation systems.

I would like to highlight two important classes of collaborative filtering, one is the similarity-based neighbourhood approach and the other is the latent factor model. The latter will be discussed in more detail in the next chapter (1.4).

The neighbourhood approach of collaborative filtering focuses on similarity of items or similarity of users, depending on the task at hand. But it is very important to highlight, that this similarity is based on previous feedback (for example ratings) that the users gave to the items, not the similarity of users as people or items as subjects. The whole idea of collaborative filtering is not to use any metadata about users or items, only the explicit feedback.

A very good illustration, taken from [9], is given in Figure 1. On the left-hand side, we can see an explanation of the so-called user-based collaborative

Figure 1: Collaborative filtering [9]

filtering, that uses the similarity of users based on the feedback they gave. The figure has arrows that symbolize that a given user likes a given item. So user 1 likes grapes, strawberry, watermelon and orange. User 2 only likes strawberry. User 3 likes strawberry and watermelon. From these given feedback, we can intuitively say that user 1 and user 3 are similar, meaning that they have similar taste, and like almost the same things. So if we want to recommend an item to user 3, we can look at the items that the similar user 1 likes, and based on that, recommend for user 3 grapes and orange. This is how the user-based collaborative filtering works.

On the right-hand side of the figure, we can see the item-based collaborative filtering. This uses the similarities of items based on given feedback. The arrows mean the same as before, so user 1 likes grapes, strawberry, watermelon and orange. User 2 likes grapes and watermelon. User 3 likes watermelon. Using this, we can intuitively say that grapes and watermelon are similar, because if someone likes one of these items, then they probably like the other one too. Based on this, if we want to recommend an item to

user 3, who likes watermelon, we can recommend an item similar to watermelon. So we would recommend grapes.

These methods can of course be extended to huge data sets. For example, consider a large matrix with rows representing each user and columns representing each item. The elements of the matrix can be binary values, expressing whether a user likes an item, or each element of the matrix can be a rating on a scale of 1-5. This rating matrix is usually a sparse matrix, because not every user rated every item. User-based collaborative filtering, which is a similarity-based neighbourhood approach as mentioned above, aims to recommend an item to a given user. This can be achieved by calculating the similarities of the given user with all the other users, and then recommending an item that is not rated by the given user yet, but highly rated by the most similar user. The users are represented as rows of the matrix, so the similarities are computed between rows as vectors.

The item-based collaborative filtering can be interpreted analogously. The only difference is that in this case, we have to calculate the similarities of the column vectors.

There are many ways to define a similarity function depending on the task at hand or the data available. Two of the most often used functions in collaborative filtering to calculate similarities of vectors are cosine similarity and Pearson correlation. To define these functions, let R denote the $m \times n$ dimensional ratings matrix with m users and n items. Let I_u denote the set of item indices for which ratings have been specified by user (row) u . We define the cosine similarity between users u and v as

$$\text{Cosine}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\sum_{k \in I_u \cap I_v} r_{uk} \cdot r_{vk}}{\sqrt{\sum_{k \in I_u \cap I_v} r_{uk}^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{k \in I_u \cap I_v} r_{vk}^2}}. \quad (1)$$

Cosine similarity measures the angle between the rating vectors. If the angle is 0° , then they are vectors having the same orientation and if the angle is 180° , then they are highly dissimilar vectors.

Pearson correlation is actually a centered cosine similarity. We subtract the mean ratings from the user ratings, so that the mean is centered at 0, and then calculate the cosine similarity. Pearson correlation between users u and v is defined as

$$\text{Pearson}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\sum_{k \in I_u \cap I_v} (r_{uk} - \mu_u) \cdot (r_{vk} - \mu_v)}{\sqrt{\sum_{k \in I_u \cap I_v} (r_{uk} - \mu_u)^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{k \in I_u \cap I_v} (r_{vk} - \mu_v)^2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } \mu_u = \frac{\sum_{k \in I_u} r_{uk}}{|I_u|} \quad \forall u \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (3)$$

A different approach is when we consider the metadata about users or items. This is the so called content-based recommendation. This method can be very useful if we would like to incorporate the information we have about the users and the items, or if we do not have access to any ratings from the users. Without any data about past user interactions we cannot use collaborative filtering, in which case content-based method is a good alternative.

Figure 2: Content-based filtering [9]

Figure 2 shows the main idea of this approach. We have a user who likes an article, and we have another article that is similar to the one they liked. Then we can recommend this other article to the user.

The most important difference between collaborative filtering and content-based filtering is that in the case of context-based filtering we calculate the similarities purely based on the metadata. So we do not use any ranking matrix, but the known attributes of the items or the users. This method can also be extended to huge datasets (e.g. item catalogues or user databases).

The item-based version calculates similarities between items, where an item is represented by a corresponding vector with the attribute values. For example, if the item is an article, then the attributes can be the title, author, date, length, topic, or even features extracted from the text itself, etc. So if a user likes an item, then we calculate the similarities of that particular item with all the other items, and we recommend the most similar one.

The user-based version works analogously. In this case, we need metadata about the users. So if we want to recommend an item to a specific user A, we first calculate the similarities of that user with all the other users. Then we take into account the most similar user, and select an item that is liked or highly rated by the most similar user, and we recommend that item to the original user A.

Finally, a very powerful neighborhood based method is described in [10].

1.4 Matrix factorization

Many of the most successful realizations of latent factor models for recommendation are based on matrix factorization (MF) [4]. Basically, matrix factorization represents both users and items by vectors of latent factors extracted from the rating patterns. The MF method decomposes the rating matrix R into a product of two lower rank matrices $R \approx PQ$. The rows of P are the user feature vectors (p_u) , and the columns of Q are the item feature vectors (q_i) .

Matrix factorization models utilize a technique where users and items are represented in a joint latent factor space of a dimension denoted by f . In this space, the interactions between users and items are represented as inner products. Each user u is represented by a vector $p_u \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times f}$, and item i is represented by a vector $q_i \in \mathbb{R}^{f \times 1}$. In the context of a specific item i , the components of q_i quantify the item’s possession of various latent factors, whether positive or negative. Likewise, concerning a particular user u , the components of p_u gauge the user’s level of interest in items characterized by corresponding factors, also potentially positive or negative. The resulting dot product $p_u \cdot q_i$ encapsulates the interaction between user u and item i , effectively representing the user’s overall interest in the item’s attributes. This approximation mirrors user u ’s rating of item i , denoted as r_{ui} , leading to the estimation:

$$\hat{r}_{ui} = p_u \cdot q_i \tag{4}$$

The primary challenge lies in computing the mapping of each item and user to factor vectors q_i and p_u in the latent factor space of dimension f . Once this mapping is established by the recommendation system, it becomes straightforward to estimate the rating that a user would assign to any item using Equation 4.

To learn the factor vectors p_u and q_i , the system minimizes the regularized squared error on the set of known ratings:

$$\min_{p,q} \sum_{(u,i) \in \kappa} (r_{ui} - p_u \cdot q_i)^2 + \lambda(\|p_u\|_2^2 + \|q_i\|_2^2) \tag{5}$$

Here, κ represents the set of (u, i) pairs for which r_{ui} is known (the training set). The system learns the model by adjusting the factor vectors to best fit the observed ratings. However, the objective is to generalize beyond these observed ratings to predict future, unknown ratings accurately. Therefore, the system must prevent overfitting the observed data by regularizing the

learned parameters, penalizing their magnitude. The constant λ controls the degree of regularization and is typically determined through cross-validation.

It is often worth including bias in the model. The motivation for this is that a significant portion of the observed variation in rating values stems from factors associated with either users or items, termed as biases or intercepts, which operate independently of any interactions. For instance, in typical collaborative filtering datasets, certain users tend to consistently give higher ratings than others, while some items tend to consistently receive higher ratings than others. This reflects the general perception that certain products are superior or inferior to others.

Consequently, it would be imprudent to attribute the entire rating value solely to the interaction between $p_u \cdot q_i$. Instead, the system aims to discern the portion of these values that can be explained by individual user or item biases. Thus, it subjects only the genuine interaction portion of the data to factor modeling.

Biases expand Equation 4 as follows:

$$\hat{r}_{ui} = b_u + b_i + p_u \cdot q_i \quad (6)$$

In this equation, the observed rating is decomposed into three components: user bias, item bias, and the interaction between the user and item. This breakdown enables each component to account for only the relevant part of the signal. The system learns by minimizing the squared error function[11]:

$$\min_{p,q,b} \sum_{(u,i) \in \kappa} (r_{ui} - b_u - b_i - p_u \cdot q_i)^2 + \lambda(\|p_u\|_2^2 + \|q_i\|_2^2 + b_u^2 + b_i^2) \quad (7)$$

1.5 Neural networks

In this chapter, artificial neural networks are presented, which are often used in data science and also serve as the basis of some recommendation system models. These networks are inspired by biological neural networks, modelling

some of their properties and operation. For clarity, I will henceforth use the term neural networks to refer to artificial neural networks.

Neural networks can approximate any function [12], making the models suitable for both regression and classification tasks. They also have the important advantage of being able to independently derive new attributes. This is not the case for simple machine learning algorithms, where we have to determine which new attributes are worth introducing.

Figure 3: Structure of a neuron [13]

The smallest unit in a neural network is the perceptron, also known as a neuron (Figure 3). The input vertices are where the attribute values arrive, and there is also a distinguished input constant member. Each input has a weight, these weights will have to be learned by the model. The central vertex is where the counting is done, by summing the values of the inputs multiplied by their weights. A chosen activation function is then applied to the resulting value, and the result determines the output of the neuron. Depending on the task, this may be a binary value (above a given threshold the output is 1, below a threshold index it is 0) or a continuous value (representing, for example, the probability of belonging to a class).

A neural network is a connected set of several neurons. These are organised in layers (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Structure of a neural network [14]

The first layer contains the input vertices, followed by any number of hidden layers, and finally the output layer. The neurons in the adjacent layers are connected, meaning that the outputs of a neuron or neurons in one layer are the inputs of neurons in the next layer. Exactly how the neurons of successive layers are connected depends on the type and architecture of the neural network. The weights of the connections between neurons can be set independently and must be learned by the algorithm in such a way as to minimize a predefined objective function.

In cases where a neural network contains several hidden layers, we talk about deep learning.

The neural network is usually trained with the stochastic gradient method as follows: we first initialize the weights. We randomly take a record from the training set and give it as input to the neural network. The record is passed through the neural network, and calculating with the current weights an output is obtained. This is compared with the expected target value, i.e. the

deviation (error) is calculated using the appropriate error function. Then the error is propagated back, which means that the local gradient is calculated for each weight, and then the weights are updated. This is repeated with more and more training data until the error is minimal.

The local gradient for a multi-layer neural network can be calculated using the chain rule.

Figure 5: Introduction of notations [15]

$$x_i^{l+1} = g \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ji}^l x_j^l + w_0^l \right) \quad (8)$$

Let us denote the neurons and weights as shown in Figure 5, and let F denote the error function, \hat{y} the output, and g the activation function. The output of a given neuron can be computed using formula (8). The sum sums up the inputs to a given vertex (so n is the number of neurons in the previous layer), and l runs from 0 to the number of neurons in the second to last layer ($L - 1$). The local gradient can be obtained using the following formula:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial w_{jk}^l} = \sum_{mn\dots q} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \hat{y}} \frac{\partial \hat{y}}{\partial x_m^L} \frac{\partial x_m^L}{\partial x_n^{L-1}} \dots \frac{\partial x_q^{l+2}}{\partial x_k^{l+1}} \frac{\partial x_k^{l+1}}{\partial w_{jk}^l} \quad (9)$$

where L is the total number of layers, and m, n, \dots, q run through the numbers of neurons in a layer.

Figure 6: We have to sum the gradients for the different paths [15]

The stochastic gradient method mentioned above aims to find the minimum location of the error function. The basic idea of the method is to calculate the local gradient value for a selected record and then update the weights accordingly. In this way, we always move a small step increment towards the largest decrease ($-\text{grad } f$). This will converge to a minimum location after a sufficient number of iterations.

A similar method is the gradient method, which works almost exactly the same as the stochastic gradient method. The only difference is that in each step, the gradient is calculated on the whole training dataset, the weights are updated and the step is continued. In the stochastic gradient method, only one randomly chosen record is used at each step.

The gradient method converges to a local minimum location after a sufficient number of iterations. To avoid finding only a local minimum, it is worth starting the iteration from several random starting points. However, the stochastic gradient method in many cases does not stop at local minimum locations, and therefore it is usually able to find the global minimum location. This is an active area of research, thus the reason for this phenomenon is not completely known yet.

There are several types of neural networks. The most important of these

are fully connected feed-forward neural networks, recurrent neural networks and convolutional neural networks.

In a fully connected feed-forward neural network, each neuron in adjacent layers is connected to every neuron in the next layer. The connections are only forward, there is no feedback. A disadvantage of this type is that it needs to be optimized for a lot of parameters and tends to be overfitted.

Figure 7: Overfitting, underfitting [16]

By overfitting, we mean that the model is too complicated, too complex and thus learns about correlations that are just coincidences. In this case, the training set error will be very small, but the generalisation ability of the model will be poor, so the test set error will be large. At the other extreme is underfitting, in which case the model is not sufficiently nuanced, so the error on both the training and the test set is large. This is illustrated in Figure 7.

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are also fully connected, but here there are feedbacks, i.e. directed circuits in the architecture. These are useful for sequential data sets, for example, because they can learn the time course of

the data. The RNN can also use its own internal memory, for example, for text data it can remember the order of words. It is the most commonly used type for speech recognition and natural language processing.

In convolutional neural networks (CNNs), not all connections between adjacent layers are indented. This type takes into account the “proximity” of the input data. This means that it preserves adjacency. It therefore works with fewer parameters than a fully connected network. It is most often used in image processing, where the proximity of pixels is very important, so it is very useful to exploit the functionality of this type.

1.6 Attention mechanism

The attention mechanism is described in the article *Attention Is All You Need* [17] as part of the Transformer model architecture, and the aim is to improve natural language models with this new method [18]. However, attention mechanism itself can be used in any neural network as an independent layer.

The attention mechanism is used in machine learning and natural language processing to enhance model accuracy by prioritizing relevant data. It empowers the model to focus on specific regions of the input data, assigning greater importance to essential features while disregarding less relevant ones. Each input attribute receives a weight according to its significance in achieving the desired output.

As stated in the original article [17], attention (also called Scaled Dot-Product Attention) can be regarded as a function that takes a query along with a collection of key-value pairs as input, and maps them to an output. The queries, keys, values and outputs are all represented as vectors. The output is determined by calculating a weighted sum of the values, where the weight assigned to each value is computed by a compatibility function of the query with the corresponding key.

Let d_k denote the dimension of the input query and key vectors, and let d_v denote the dimension of the input value vectors. The attention function

calculates the dot product of the query with all keys, and then divide each by $\sqrt{d_k}$ and apply a softmax function (defined in Equation (10)) to get the weights on the values.

$$\text{softmax}(\mathbf{z})_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{z_j}} \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, N \text{ and } \mathbf{z} = (z_1, \dots, z_N) \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (10)$$

In practice, Scaled Dot-Product Attention is not calculated one by one for each query, but is computed in parallel for a set of queries, packed together into a matrix Q . The keys and values are also packed together into matrices K and V . The output matrix is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (11)$$

Figure 8: Scaled Dot-Product Attention [17]

The calculation of the scaled dot-product attention is illustrated in Figure 8. Dot-product attention is very fast and space-efficient in practice, because there exist highly optimized matrix multiplication algorithms, which can be used for the implementation of this calculation.

The normalizing or scaling factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ is used for avoiding the so called vanishing gradient effect. For large values of d_k , the dot product can grow very large, which causes the fact that the softmax function will have extremely small gradients. The reason for the possibility of the dot product growing very large is the following: assume that the components of vectors q and k are independent random variables with mean 0 and variance 1. Then the dot product $q \cdot k = \sum_{i=1}^{d_k} q_i k_i$ has mean 0 and variance d_k .

The vanishing gradient effect means, that when training a model, these small gradients will change the weights only by negligibly small amounts, so the model will not learn that effectively. So it is very useful that the attention function is defined this way, because this effect cannot happen.

So far we have only talked about calculating a single attention function, but there exists the so called Multi-Head Attention, which can perform multiple Scaled Dot-Product calculations simultaneously. Multi-Head Attention uses h (where h denotes the number of heads) linear projections of the queries, keys and values with different, learned weight matrices, that project the d_{input} -dimensional input to d_k , d_k and d_v dimensions respectively. Then we perform the above described attention function parallel on each of these projected versions of queries, keys and values, and we get d_v -dimensional output values. Then we concatenate these, and use another linear projection to get the final output values. The calculation of the Multi-Head Attention is illustrated in Figure 9. The formal definition of Multi-Head Attention can be seen here:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) &= \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h)W^O \\ &\text{where } \text{head}_i = \text{Attention}(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VW_i^V) \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where the linear projections are parameter matrices $W_i^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{input} \times d_k}$, $W_i^K \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{input} \times d_k}$, $W_i^V \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{input} \times d_v}$ and $W^O \in \mathbb{R}^{hd_v \times d_{input}}$.

Figure 9: Multi-Head Attention [17]

1.7 The aim of this thesis

In this thesis, I focus on the task to predict explicit rating values (elements of a given rating matrix). In each experiment, I use a training dataset to train different models, and a test dataset to evaluate these models and compare the results.

I implemented the similarity based collaborative filtering models, the content based model, the TopPopular model, and also the matrix factorization model. For this last one, I created a neural network model implementation.

Matrix factorization is a relatively simple method, but in practice it often achieves better results than other models [4]. Based on this, my task was to investigate whether incorporating attention mechanism into the matrix factorization model can achieve a better performance. Additionally, I conducted various experiments to assess whether further architectural modifications could outperform the result of the original matrix factorization model.

Finally, I compared all the different methods and determined which model offers the best performance for this specific task.

2 Methods

2.1 Exploratory data analysis

Before we start working with the data, it is worth taking a closer look at what information is actually available.

For this thesis I used the MovieLens 100k dataset [19], which contains 100,000 ratings (on the scale of 1–5) from 943 users on 1682 movies.

During the coding process, these ratings were randomly split into training and test sets in the ratio 80%-20%. The models were trained on the training set and their performance was measured on the unrated cells of the test set.

The format of the data is csv files, so the records are the rows of the table, the attributes are the columns of the table. We have a rating dataframe, one record contains one user, one item and a rating. We can turn this dataframe into a ranking matrix, which contains users as rows, and items as columns. The cell R_{ij} is the rating of item j by user i . As mentioned before, the dataset contains 100,000 ratings from 943 users on 1682 movies. This means, that the ranking matrix has dimension 943×1682 , but has only 100,000 non-empty cells. So the density of this dataset is about 6.3%, which is extremely sparse.

We also have a file with some attributes of the items (title, release date, imdb url, genre), and an other one with some attributes of the users (age, sex, occupation, zip code).

As part of the exploratory data analysis, it is also worth creating some easy-to-understand diagrams to highlight and illustrate the important features of the records. For example, the number and percentage of different rating values, the number of ratings per movies, the number of movies grouped by genre, what are the top 10 genres with most ratings or what are the mean movie ratings per genre. I present and interpret the figures in the Results section (Section 3.1).

2.2 Implementation of similarity based methods

As I explained in Section 1.3, there are two main methods based on similarity. The first one is the collaborative filtering, and the other one is the content-based recommendation.

For the former one, I had to use the ratings dataframe, that contains three columns: `user_id`, `movie_id` and the rating. I created a sparse rating matrix R from this data, each row represents a user, and each column represents an item (movie). A cell is empty, if the user did not rate the item, otherwise the cell contains the rating.

At the user-based collaborative filtering, I had to calculate similarities between the rows of the matrix as vectors. As the task was to predict ratings, it was important, not to use only the one most similar user, but more of them, and calculate some kind of average of their ratings. For this, I decided to use the k-nearest neighbour (knn) method [20], [21]. This is a well-known approach in data science. In our case, with this method I could easily predict ratings in the following way: first I had to choose a similarity function. I used the cosine similarity and later also the Pearson correlation, to see which one performs better. Then for each cell in the test set, I had to predict a rating. So for predicting R_{ij} I used the knn method to get the k nearest neighbours of the row vector i (we only regard users who rated item j), and calculate the rating with a weighted average based on the similarities.

The knn method calculates the similarities of row vector i and all the other row vectors, and selects the k most similar ones, and takes only these into account. For k I used the default value 40. So we get the 40 most similar row vectors with row i , and also the similarity values. Then we calculate \hat{R}_{ij} (the prediction of R_{ij}) as the similarity-score weighted average of the 40 neighbour's ratings of item j :

$$\hat{R}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{u \in N^k(i)} \text{similarity}(i, u) \cdot R_{uj}}{\sum_{u \in N^k(i)} \text{similarity}(i, u)} \quad (13)$$

where $N^k(i)$ is the set of the k nearest neighbours of i .

The item-based collaborative filtering is analogue. The difference is, that in this case we have to calculate the similarities between the column vectors. Here I also used cosine similarity and Pearson correlation too. The prediction \hat{R}_{ij} is calculated the same way as before. I used knn with 40 neighbours. So here, we get the 40 most similar items (we only regard items that were rated by user i), and also the similarity-scores, then we calculate the similarity-score weighted average of the ratings of user i for the 40 neighbour items:

$$\hat{R}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{v \in N^k(j)} \text{similarity}(j, v) \cdot R_{iv}}{\sum_{v \in N^k(j)} \text{similarity}(j, v)} \quad (14)$$

For the content based recommendation, I used the metadata given for the items. The similarity was calculated based on this, and not the rating matrix. I created a one-hot encoded vector for each item with the genres as attributes. Then I used cosine similarity to calculate the similarities of these vectors. The prediction \hat{R}_{ij} was computed with knn, but the 40 most similar items were calculated purely on the metadata. Of course, items that were not rated by user i were excluded from the neighbours. Equation (14) can be used for this case also, but it must be noted, that the similarity function is calculated on the metadata vectors of items j and v .

The metadata given for users was not sufficient enough, so it would not have been worthwhile to calculate similarities based on that.

The knn method can be effective, even if there is not enough neighbours in the dataset. This can occur for example if an item in the test set was rated by less than 40 users. This does not mean any problem, because knn simply reduces the parameter k in these cases to a value, that can be used.

I also created a TopPopular model that is not based on similarity, just to compare the results, to see whether incorporating similarities into recommendations can improve performance or not. This TopPopular model is very basic. It calculates the average rating for each item separately in the training set, then takes the top 10 “most popular” movies (the 10 items with the

highest average rating). If there are more movies with the same average rating value, then the one with a higher amount of ratings is considered to be better. I also calculated the overall average rating in the training set (sum of all ratings divided by the total number of ratings). The prediction \hat{R}_{ij} is the average rating for item j if it is in the top 10 items (regardless of user i), otherwise the prediction is the overall average.

2.3 Neural network model for matrix factorization

As already mentioned in Section 1.4, the aim of matrix factorization is to find representations for both items and users by vectors of latent factors extracted from the rating patterns. Then we can predict a certain rating with the dot product of the user latent vector and the item latent vector.

This method can be efficiently implemented using neural networks [22]. For the implementation of the models, I opted for PyTorch. First I had to preprocess the dataset for the model training. This was a simple remapping of indices, because there were 943 unique user ids, and 1653 unique item ids in the training dataset, but these were not in the needed $[0, 942]$ and $[0, 1652]$ forms. This remapping is important for reducing memory usage in the model's embeddings.

The original dataset had 943 unique user ids and 1682 unique item ids, but after splitting it into training and test sets, only 1653 unique movies appeared in the training set. The 29 movies appearing only in the test set would have posed a problem, because not being in the training set means those would not have any trained latent vectors, so we could not predict ratings for those movies with this model. To solve this issue, these 29 items were simply removed from the test set.

So the preprocessed dataset has user ids, item ids, and ratings. Each user and movie (item) is put through an nn.Embedding layer. This layer creates the vector representation. Then the user embedding and item embedding vectors are multiplied together and summed (equivalent to a dot product).

This is the simplest way of matrix factorization. However, it is often advised to also add biases and weight initialization into the model, to improve performance. User biases help compensating the fact, that some users rate movies, on average, higher than other users. Item biases have a similar idea. For example, higher quality items might be rated higher, on average, than low quality items. So I also included a user bias embedding layer, and an item bias embedding layer, and added to the rating prediction dot product these two bias values similar to Equation (6).

Each layer in a neural network has weights, and in most cases these are randomly initialized based on a given predefined distribution. With weight initialization, we can change this predefined distribution to a selected one. The layer `nn.Embedding` is initialized with a normal distribution $(0, 1)$ by default. I changed the weight initialization by the user and item embeddings to uniform between $[0, 0.01]$ and by user and item biases to uniform between $[-0.01, 0.01]$. This empirically performs better than the defaults.

The number of latent factors is the dimension of the embedding vector of users and items. I chose this to be 200. Therefore, user embedding matrix has size 943×200 , and the item embedding matrix has size 1653×200 . This means that using this user embedding matrix, we get a 200 dimensional latent vector for each user, and also for each item using the item embedding matrix. The user bias is an embedding matrix sized 943×1 , and the item bias embedding matrix is sized 1653×1 , because these do not assign vectors to the users and items, but only one dimensional bias values.

The training of the model consist of epochs. One epoch is done, when all the training data ran through once the neural network. The network uses batches, which means that training samples are not used one by one but together in blocks. After each batch the weights are updated (in order to minimalize the loss). The model has access to the ratings in the training set, so it can calculate the loss as the function of the predicted rating value and the actual rating value (exact error function definition will be discussed in

Section 2.6). For the loss function minimalization, I used the adam optimizer method [23]. The batch size is set to be 64.

After each epoch, we obtain the training loss and the validation loss values as feedback on model quality. The former tells us how well the model performs on the already known training data, and the latter shows how well can the model generalize for unknown data. The validation set here is the test set I separated at the beginning.

It is also possible to set the initial learning rate of the model, which affects the rate at which weights are updated. For this I chose 10^{-4} , and I used the `torch.optim.lr_scheduler.ReduceLROnPlateau` method for dynamically reducing the learning rate if needed. For the parameters I chose patience to be 5 and factor to be 0.1. This means that if the validation loss does not decrease in 5 epochs, the learning rate is multiplied by 0.1. This can help preventing overfitting.

Another way of avoiding overfitting is to use early stopping. I implemented this method for the training. It has a patience parameter, that defines the number of epochs after which the training stops if there is no improvement regarding the validation loss. I set this parameter to 20.

Later in the Results section, I will refer to this model as the MF_bias model.

2.4 Extension of the MF model with attention mechanism

There are several methods that incorporate attention mechanism into the MF model [24], [25], [26], [27], [28]. My goal was to test certain ideas that might improve recommendation performance.

Our own new idea (proposed by Kelen Domokos Miklós) was to replace the dot product with the attention mechanism, because a neural network can have difficulty learning the dot product [29]. I created a model (it will be referred as MF_Attention model) that is based on the MF_bias model but

has some modifications. The embedding layers for users, items, user biases and item biases and also the weight initializations are the same. There is an additional `hidden_dim` parameter, and also some new layers and transformations.

First the model creates the user, item and biases embedding vectors with the embedding layers. Then it concatenates the user and item embedding vectors, and this $2 * 200 = 400$ dimensional vector serves as the input for a linear layer, that simply transforms the 400 dimensional input vector into a `hidden_dim` dimensional vector. This `hidden_dim` is set to be 500 in this model. This output vector is then used as the input for the next layer, that is a `nn.MultiheadAttention` layer. This layer works exactly as the Multi-Head Attention function described in Section 1.6 in Equation (12). In this layer I set the parameters as follows: the model uses 10 parallel attention heads, which means that the 500 dimensional input is split into 10 vectors with dimension 50, and each head gets one of these vectors. Also, the input query, key and value are the same vectors here, so this layer actually calculates self attention in this case. The output of the attention layer is a vector, same dimensional as the input. But we need a single value for the prediction, so I just simply summed up the elements of the vector (this is called pooling), and the final output of the model is this summed attention value plus the user bias and the item bias.

The batch size is 64, the embedding size is 200, the initial learning rate is 10^{-4} , and I also used early stopping and `ReduceLROnPlateau` for training this model.

This approach clearly replaces the dot product calculation in the original matrix factorization model with the attention mechanism, but unfortunately this initial attention based model did not outperform the `MF_bias` model. Thus, further experimentations with architectural modifications of the model were needed.

2.5 Model improvement attempts via additional layers and parameter optimization

I tried several modifications, and for each architectural change I trained a new model and checked if the performance has improved or not.

The first idea was to change the `hidden_dim` parameter in the model. I created a model with `hidden_dim` 1000 and also another one with 1200. By 1000 for example, the linear layer transforms the 400 dimensional input into a 1000 dimensional output, and then in the attention layer, every one of the 10 heads gets a 100 dimensional vector.

I also tried changing the number of parallel attention heads, so I experimented with 5, 10 and 20 of them.

As mentioned before, biases can help in a lot of cases, but it can also happen, that these do not improve the performance of the model. Based on this idea, I made versions of these models without any bias values. This means, that there is no embedding layer for biases, and at the end of the model, the output is simply calculated with pooling the output vector of the attention layer.

Layer normalization is a technique used to normalize the outputs of a layer in a neural network to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This layer implements the operation as described in the original paper Layer Normalization [30]. This method is particularly useful for models with complex architectures, such as transformer networks and recurrent neural networks, as it usually helps stabilize training and improve convergence. I used this layer on the output of the linear layer.

A commonly used regularization method to avoid overfitting is applying dropout to the layers of the neural network. It was introduced by Geoffrey Hinton and his colleagues in 2012 [31]. Dropout works by randomly “dropping out” (setting to zero) a certain proportion p of neurons or units in a layer during training, effectively turning them off. This introduces noise during training and helps the network learn more robust features. This can be

applied to any layer in the neural network, and p is a parameter we can set. By randomly dropping out neurons, dropout helps prevent the model from relying too heavily on specific neurons, encouraging it to learn more general patterns from the data. This can lead to better generalization and improved performance on unseen data. First I tried adding dropout to only the linear layer, then for the embedding layers as well. I also experimented with various values for the parameter.

Linear layers often have some activation function on the output, so I made some versions of the models where I added a ReLU activation function to the linear layer. This function is defined the following way: $f(x) = \max(0, x)$.

Incorporating more layers into the neural network, for example via stacking attention layers on each other, can offer several benefits. Adding depth to a model by stacking layers can increase its ability to model complex relationships and interactions within the data. This added depth can help the model learn more abstract and high-level features. I tried this method with 2 stacked attention layers, then with 3 and also with 4. The first attempt was to just simply stack these layers in a way, that the output of the first is the input of the second, etc. Then I used the so called residual connection between the attention layers. This means that the input of the second attention layer is $F(x) + x$, where x is the input of the first layer and $F(x)$ is the output of the first layer. So we add the identity function of the previous layer's input to the previous layer's output, and this is the input for the next layer. This method helps to maintain the information flow throughout the network and prevents the gradients from vanishing. The residual connection is a shortcut that allows the information to bypass one or more layers in the network and reach the output directly.

Later I also made some experiments with applying dropout for each attention layer.

For the parameter optimization, I tried various different values for the embedding size, and for the p parameter of the dropout layers. I also made

experiments with changing the batch size by the training, I used 128, 64, 32 and 16.

2.6 Model evaluation method

When evaluating recommendation system models, one of the most common metrics used is the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). RMSE measures the average magnitude of the errors between predicted and actual values, providing a clear indication of how well the model is performing in terms of prediction accuracy. Lower RMSE values indicate better performance, as the predictions are closer to the actual values.

RMSE is calculated the following way:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (15)$$

where y_i is the actual value for instance i , \hat{y}_i is the predicted value for instance i and N is the total number of instances.

Regarding our dataset, y_i is an actual rating, \hat{y}_i is a predicted rating, and N is the size of the set, we are currently evaluating.

To evaluate the neural network models effectively, we can monitor RMSE on both the training set and a separate validation set (this is the test set in our case).

Training error measures how well the model fits the training data. Monitoring the training RMSE can help us understand how well the model is learning from the training set. It is calculated after each batch during training, and we get a feedback after each epoch, so the value we see is the average error of the batches.

Validation error measures how well the model generalizes to unseen data. By tracking the RMSE on a validation set, we can assess the model's performance on data it has not seen during training. This helps us ensure the

model is learning to generalize and not just memorizing the training data. This validation error is calculated after each epoch, on the test set.

The models based on similarity, which did not use neural networks for training, learned on the training dataset, and I evaluated them on the separated test set.

3 Results

3.1 Results of exploratory data analysis

As mentioned before, we have a sparse ranking matrix of size 943×1682 , but it has only 100,000 non empty cells. And I also used some metadata about the items for the content-based recommendation method, so the dataframe with the attributes of the movies is also important. I have created figures to illustrate some of the important features of the data. The first one (Figure 10) shows the number of occurrence of each possible rating $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

Figure 10: Number and percentage of rating values

It is clear from Figure 10 that people tend to give rather higher ratings (3,4,5) than lower ones (1,2). Rating 4 is the most common one, then rating 3 and rating 5 follow. The least common is rating 1, which is the worst possible option to give.

I selected the top 10 movies with the most ratings, to see how many people rated these ones. This can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Number and percentage of ratings for the top 10 movies

The most commonly rated movie is Star Wars, then Contact, Fargo and Return of the Jedi follow.

Using the movie dataframe, the most important attribute is the genre, because that was used in the content-based recommendation. The related histogram (Figure 12) shows the number and percentage of movies in each genre.

Figure 12: Number and percentage of movies in each genre

Most movies (25.8%) are dramas, but there are also many comedies (18.0%) in the dataset. 8.9% of the movies are action movies, another 8.9% are thrillers, and 8.8% are romance movies. The rest of the genres are each less than 5% of all movies.

I also wanted to gain insight into the most rated genres, so I made a histogram for showing the top 5 genres with the most ratings (Figure 13).

Dramas get the most ratings, then comedies, action, thriller and romance follow. This is the same order as the order of number of movies in each genre (Figure 12). So the genres with the most movies get the most ratings.

On the other hand, if we look at the mean ratings per genre, the order changes. This can be seen in Figure 14.

The highest mean rating belongs to the genre Film-Noir, then drama, no genre, and documentary follow etc.

Figure 13: Top 5 genres with the most ratings

Figure 14: Mean ratings for each genre

3.2 Similarity based methods evaluation

In this section, I present the results of the models created using the similarity based methods described in Section 2.2.

There are two item-based collaborative filtering models, the only difference between them is the similarity function I used. By one of them, it was the cosine similarity, by the other one it was the Pearson correlation. These models will be referred to as Item KNN (cosine) and Item KNN (pearson).

There are also two user-based collaborative filtering models, the difference is the same here. These will be referred to as User KNN (cosine) and User KNN (pearson).

I also made a content based recommendation system model, which I will refer to as Content KNN.

And the last method I described in Section 2.2 is the TopPopular model, and the sole purpose of this basic model is to compare its result with the performance of the other models.

For the evaluation of these models, I used the RMSE error function. The results can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of the similarity based models

Model	RMSE
Item KNN (cosine)	1.0311
Item KNN (pearson)	1.0426
User KNN (cosine)	1.0207
User KNN (pearson)	1.0147
Content KNN	1.0734
TopPopular	1.2731

3.3 MF model evaluation

The matrix factorization method was implemented by creating a neural network model [22], as described in Section 2.3. In this case, I have access to the training and validation error (RMSE loss) for each epoch during model training. This can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Training and validation losses during the training of the MF_bias model

The final best performance of this MF_bias model was the RMSE value of 0.8995.

3.4 Attention based models evaluation

The first attempt of including attention mechanism into the MF_bias model was detailed in Section 2.4. The RMSE of this MF_Attention model is 0.9090, so it did not outperform the original matrix factorization model.

The results of the improvement attempts and parameter optimization discussed in Section 2.5 are presented in this section.

The removal of bias value from the models helped improving the performance in most cases. The MF_Attention model without biases (Att_no_bias) has an RMSE value 0.9075 for example, which is better than with biases included.

Experimenting with various embedding sizes showed, that the value 200 is the best decision for this parameter.

I also tried different batch sizes, and a batch size of 16 seems to be optimal for training. Att_no_bias with batch size 16 has an RMSE value 0.9002.

The parameter hidden_dim in the model was originally 500, but with 1000 it made an improvement (Att_1000), and I got an RMSE 0.8976. The training and validation errors in each epoch can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Training and validation losses during the training of the Att_1000 model

This 0.8976 RMSE is better than the performance of the MF_bias original

matrix factorization model. Thus, at this point I managed to outperform the MF model with an attention based model, which was the aim of my thesis.

However, we decided not to stop here, but try to improve the performance of the model even further.

I tried optimizing the number of parallel heads in the attention layer, but all other values than 10 increased the error.

Then I added layer normalization to the linear layer, but it did not help. However, layer normalization together with dropout to the linear and embedding layers and a `hidden_dim` of 500 (`Att_ln_dr_500`) helped improving the performance, I got an RMSE of 0.8957.

Adding an activation function (ReLU) to the linear layer did not decrease the error of the model.

I tried removing the layer normalization from the `Att_ln_dr_500` model, and the new model I got (`Att_dr_500`) made an improvement in performance, the new RMSE was 0.8915. Optimizing the dropout parameter led to the value 0.35, and so the RMSE improved further to 0.8899. Then I changed the `hidden_dim` to 1000, but the RMSE got higher with this change to 0.8959.

The next approach was to increase the number of attention layers. First I simply stacked two attention layers. This got an RMSE value of 0.8978. Adding dropout to the attention layers did not increase performance. Then I included residual connection between the two attention layers, without dropout (`2att_res`) and this helped a little, I got RMSE 0.8919 but it was still not better than the best result so far. Adding layer normalization increased the error by a lot.

Stacking three attention layers after each other with residual connections (`3att_res`) achieved a new best result: 0.8893. Adding dropout to the attention layers led to even better performance (`3att_res_dr`), an RMSE of 0.8889. Optimizing batch size and the dropout parameter shows, that the batch size of 16 and dropout parameter 0.35 was optimal for this model, and

with these values the RMSE improved even further, to 0.8884. The training and validation errors of this model for each epoch can be seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Training and validation losses during the training of the 3att_res_dr model

As we can see in Figure 17, the validation error is lower than the training error for many epochs. This may seem surprising at first, but the reason for this phenomenon is the dropout. In this model, there is dropout applied to the embedding layers, linear layer, and all the attention layers. This means that during training 35% of the neurons in these layers are “turned off”. Thus, the training error after each batch is calculated without using the previously learned value of these neuron weights, these are simply left out from the prediction. However, the validation loss is calculated at the end of the epoch, not during like the training error, and also, dropout is not applied when the validation error is calculated. In this case, the prediction uses the learned weights of all neurons. So this is the reason for this phenomenon shown on the figure.

Later I tried stacking 4 attention layers with residual connections, using dropout on all of them (4att_res_dr), but the RMSE did not improve: 0.8886. Excluding dropout from the attention layers results in an RMSE of 0.8909. Layer normalization and adding ReLU activation function to the linear layer did not help either. The optimal hidden_dim parameter for these stacked attention models was 500, and the optimal embedding_dim was 200.

The summarized results of the most important models can be seen together in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of the attention based models

Model	RMSE
MF_Attention	0.9090
Att_no_bias	0.9002
Att_1000	0.8976
Att_ln_dr_500	0.8957
Att_dr_500	0.8899
2att_res	0.8919
3att_res_dr	0.8884
4att_res_dr	0.8886

4 Discussion

4.1 Exploratory data analysis conclusion

Most datasets are not balanced, and this can be stated in the case of MovieLens 100k dataset too. Figure 10 shows that the distribution of rating values is not uniform.

Also, the distribution of ratings for different movies is not uniform either. Figure 11 shows that movies have different amount of ratings. There are

some films with up to 600 ratings, but on the other hand there are films in the dataset with only a few ratings.

The distribution of movies in different genres can be seen in Figure 12. We can draw the conclusion, that the number of films in different genres is nowhere near uniform.

Based on Figure 13, we can conclude that there are some popular genres with much higher amount of ratings, than other not so popular genres.

Regarding the mean ratings per genre in Figure 14, we can say that these values are quite similar, even though the number of movies in each genre is very diverse.

4.2 Comparing the results of different models

The evaluation of each model is based on the RMSE value, introduced in Section 2.6. Calculating this error for each model makes it possible to compare the results.

Regarding the similarity based methods (Table 1), we can conclude that the TopPopular model is too general and has a worse performance than all the other models. Content KNN is better than the TopPopular, but worse than the collaborative filtering models. These have varying results. It seems, that the user-based collaborative filtering models perform better than the item-based ones. User KNN with Pearson correlation as similarity function has the best performance among the similarity based models.

The matrix factorization model not surprisingly outperformed the former methods.

Incorporating attention mechanism into the matrix factorization model did not make any improvement at first, but after various architectural changes and parameter optimization it outperformed the original MF_bias model. To achieve the best result, I had to remove the bias from the model, add dropout to several layers, stack attention layers with residual connections, and optimize the embedding size, hidden_dim, dropout and batch size parameters.

4.3 Summary

In my thesis, I created some similarity-based methods, a matrix factorization model and some attention mechanism based neural network models for solving an explicit rating prediction task, and after describing their theoretical background and implementation, I compared their performances. One of the main goals was to achieve an improvement in performance by incorporating the attention mechanism into the matrix factorization model. I also conducted exploratory data analysis in order to understand the data. Finally, I evaluated the performance of the models using RMSE values. Based on the comparison, the best performance was obtained by the 3att_res_dr model, which contains three stacked attention layers with residual connections. This model achieved better results than the original matrix factorization model, thus achieving the goal of this thesis and improving this result.

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